

Molybdenum : Part VI. O-Phenanthroline, 5-Nitro-o-Phenanthroline and 2, 9-Dimethyl o-Phenanthroline Complexes of Oxo-Molybdenum (V)

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Oxo-molybdenum(V) complexes with o-phenanthroline and 5 nitro and 2, 9 dimethyl substituted o-phenanthrolines of the type $[\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_3\text{Cl}_4(\text{o-phen})_2]$ have been obtained as dark chocolate red crystalline mass. Besides some 5-nitro-o-phenanthroline and 2, 9-dimethyl o-phenanthroline bridged complexes of the type $[\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_2\text{Cl}_4(\text{X})_2(\text{o-phen.})]$ (where XH = a molecule of picolinic acid, quinaldinic acid or 8-hydroxyquinoline) have also been synthesized. The complexes are all diamagnetic, have molybdenum in +5 oxidation state and provide spectra typical of oxo molybdenum(V) complexes.

O-phenanthroline and α, α' -dipyridyl complexes of oxo-molybdenum (V) have received attention. Studies with the latter ligand has been somewhat more extensive than with the former. Whereas O-phenanthroline complexes $[\text{MoOCl}_3(\text{O-phen})]^\dagger$ and $[\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_4\text{Cl}_2(\text{O-phen})_2] \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}^2$ has been described, at least three complexes, $[\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_4\text{Cl}_2(\text{dipy})_2]^3$, $[\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_3\text{Cl}_4(\text{dipy})_2]^3$ and $[\text{MoOCl}_3 \cdot \text{dipy}]^{1,2,3}$ are known with α, α' -dipyridyl. As is expected, the composition of the complexes is decided by the extent of moisture and the reaction conditions. The complex $[\text{MoOCl}_3(\text{O-phen})]$ has been synthesized by replacing the two acetonitrile groups in $[\text{MoOCl}_3 \cdot 2\text{MeCN}]^\dagger$. The complex, $[\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_4\text{Cl}_2(\text{O-phen})_2] \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ was obtained by the air oxidation of an ethanol-hydrochloric acid solution containing O-phenanthroline and $\text{K}_3[\text{MoCl}_6]$. Apparently the O-phenanthroline analogue of $[\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_3\text{Cl}_4(\text{dipy})_2]$ has not been reported as yet in the literature. Magnetic measurements have been utilised as a diagnostic tool for deciding on the extent of dimerisation in the complexes.

We selected O-phenanthroline and two other substituted O-phenanthrolines namely, the 5-nitro derivative and 2,9-dimethyl derivative as ligands for further studies. The last mentioned ligand might as well weaken the attachment of molybdenum to the heterocyclic nitrogen due to a possible steric hindrance by the two methyl groups.

Our reaction conditions, namely, anhydrous ethanol provided dark chocolate, crystalline oxo-molybdenum (V) complexes of the type $[\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_3\text{Cl}_4(\text{O-phen})_2]$ with all the selected ligands. Evidently complexation was not inhibited by the 2,9-dimethyl group. All the chelates

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registered an oxidation number of +5 for the molybdenum besides providing diamagnetic values. These properties suggested an oxygen-bridge structure of the following type :

In some of the earlier studies⁴ in this series we had described complexes of the type $[\text{MoOCl}_2\text{Q} \cdot \frac{1}{2}(\text{O-phen})]$ (where QH = quinaldinic acid or some other bidentate, monobasic acid ligand). In these complexes, it was believed that the O-phenanthroline was bridging two oxo-molybdenum(V) complex units. We also checked the generality of these synthesis with the use of 5-nitro and 2,9-dimethyl-O-phenanthroline. Thus addition of either 5-nitro O-phenanthroline or of 2,9-dimethyl O-phenanthroline to a hot solution containing one mole of MoOCl_3 and one mole of any of the inner metallic ligands such as quinaldinic acid, picolinic acid or 8-hydroxyquinoline provides crystalline precipitate of a phenanthroline bridged complex, $[\text{MoOCl}_2\text{Q} \cdot \frac{1}{2}(\text{O-phen})]$. The diamagnetic properties of these complexes indicate effective dimerisation, so that the complexes should better be treated as dimers, μ -phenanthroline chelates. We have obtained the reflectance spectra of the complex, μ -5-nitro-O-phenanthroline-dioxo-tetrachloro bisquinaldinato-dimolybdenum(V). The spectra being typical of oxo-molybdenum(V) complexes, reveals three absorption bands in the ligand field region namely, around $14,814$ – $14,084 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $18,181$ – $17,597 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $23,148$ – $22,222 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ (Fig. 1). The samples being diamagnetic, it is presumed that the ground state is a singlet and the d-d transitions occur over two oxo-molybdenum(V) centres.

Fig. 1

Fig. 1. Reflectance spectra of $[\text{MoOCl}_2\text{Q} \cdot \frac{1}{2}(\text{5-nitro O-phen})]$

TABLE I

Magnetic Measurements, Colour and Oxidation State

Compound	Colour	Magnetic property	Oxidation state
[Mo ₂ O ₃ Cl ₄ (0-phen) ₂]	Deep Chocolate	Diamagnetic	5.1
[Mo ₂ O ₃ Cl ₄ (2, 9-dimethyl 0-phen) ₂]	Brown	Diamagnetic	4.8
[Mo ₂ O ₃ Cl ₄ (5-nitro 0-phen) ₂]	Dark Chocolate	Diamagnetic	4.8
[Mo ₂ O ₂ Cl ₄ Q ₂ (2, 9-dimethyl 0-phen)]	Dark	Diamagnetic	4.8
[Mo ₂ O ₂ Cl ₄ Q ₂ (5-nitro-0-phen)]	Dark-Chocolate	Diamagnetic	5.1
[Mo ₂ O ₂ Cl ₄ (pic) ₂ (5-nitro-0-phen)]	Dark-Chocolate	Diamagnetic	4.9
[Mo ₂ O ₂ Cl ₄ (pic) ₂ (2, 9-dimethyl-0-Phen)]	Dark-Chocolate	Diamagnetic	4.8
[Mo ₂ O ₂ Cl ₄ (oxine) (5-nitro-0-phen)]	Dark-Chocolate	Diamagnetic	Not determined

5-nitro 0-phen = 5-nitro 0-phenanthroline, 2, 9-dimethyl 0-phen = 2, 9-dimethyl 0-phenanthroline; QH = quinaldinic acid; picH = picolinic acid and 0-phen = 0-phenanthroline.

EXPERIMENTAL

Ammonium oxo-pentachloro molybdate(V) (emerald green) was prepared by following standard procedure⁵. All refluxing was done on a sand bath and no special precaution was taken to exclude air and moisture.

1. *μ-oxo-dioxo-tetrachloro bis (O-phenanthroline) dimolybdenum (V) (Deep chocolate)*— Ammonium oxo-pentachloro molybdate (0.65 g.) dissolved in anhydrous ethanol (20 ml.) was filtered and this solution was added to O-phenanthroline (0.38 g.) solution in anhydrous ethanol (10 ml.). Immediately a chocolate colour precipitate formed. This was refluxed for 30 minutes, cooled, filtered, washed several times with anhydrous ethanol and dried over CaCl₂. Found: Mo, 26.3%; N, 14.7%; Cl, 18.6%. [Mo₂O₃Cl₄(O-phen)₂] requires: Mo, 25.6%; N, 15.09%, Cl, 19.1%.

2. *μ-oxo-dioxo-tetrachloro-2,9-dimethyl O-phenanthroline dimolybdenum (Brown)*— was prepared as above using 2,9-dimethyl O-phenanthroline (0.41 g.) in place of O-phenanthroline. Found: Mo, 24.8%; N, 6.6%; Cl, 17.2%. [Mo₂O₃Cl₄ (2,9-dimethyl-O-phen)] requires Mo, 24.0%; N, 7.0%; Cl, 17.9%.

3. *μ-oxo-dioxo-tetrachloro-5-nitro-O-phenanthroline dimolybdenum(V) (Dark chocolate)*— was obtained as above using 5-nitro O-phenanthroline (0.48 g.) in place of 2,9-dimethyl-O-phenanthroline. Found: Mo, 22.9%, N, 9.6%; Cl, 17.3%. [Mo₂O₃Cl₄ (5-nitro-O-phen)₂] requires: Mo, 22.6%; N, 9.9%; Cl, 16.6%.

4. μ -2,9-dimethyl *O*-phenanthroline dioxo-tetrachloro-bis(quinaldinato)-dimolybdenum(V) (*Dark*)—Quinaldinic acid (0.40 g), dissolved in anhydrous ethanol (10 ml.) was mixed with a filtered solution of ammonium oxo-pentachloro molybdate (0.65 g), dissolved in 20 ml. anhydrous ethanol. Immediately, a deep chocolate solution developed. This was then refluxed for 10 minutes and 2,9-dimethyl *O*-phenanthroline (0.21 g), dissolved in anhydrous ethanol (10 ml.) was added. Immediately, a heavy crystalline dark product formed. This was refluxed for 10 minutes, cooled, filtered, washed several times with anhydrous ethanol and finally dried over CaCl_2 . Found : Mo, 20.1%; N, 6.4%; Cl, 15.2%; $[\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_2\text{Cl}_4\text{Q}_2(2,9\text{-dimethyl } O\text{-phen})]$ requires Mo, 20.8%; N, 6.1%, Cl, 15.4%.

5. μ -5-nitro-*O*-phenanthroline dioxo-tetrachloro-bis(quinaldinato)-di molybedenum (*Dark chocolate*)* was prepared as above using 5-nitro-*O*-phenanthroline (0.25) in place of 2,9-dimethyl-*O*-phenanthroline. Found : Mo, 21.0%; N, 7.5%, Cl, 15.1%. $[\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_2\text{Cl}_4\text{Q}_2(5\text{-nitro-}O\text{-phen})]$ requires : Mo, 20.5%; N, 7.4%; Cl, 15.1%.

6. μ -5-nitro-*O*-phenanthroline dioxo-tetrachloro-bis(picolinato)-dimolybdenum(V) (*Dark chocolate*)—Picolinic acid (0.25 g), dissolved in anhydrous ethanol (10.0 ml.) was added to a filtered solution of ammonium oxo-pentachloro molybdate (V) (0.65 g.) dissolved in 10 ml. anhydrous ethanol. A deep maroon solution formed immediately. This was refluxed for 15 minutes and 5 nitro *o*-phenanthroline (0.24 g) dissolved previously in 10.0 ml. anhydrous ethanol by gentle refluxing, was added to this solution. Immediately, a crystalline maroon compound yielded. This was refluxed further for 20 minutes, cooled, filtered, washed several times with anhydrous ethanol and dried over CaCl_2 . Found : Mo, 23.2%; N, 9.0%; Cl, 17.1%. $[\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_2\text{Cl}_4(\text{Pic})_2(5\text{-nitro-}O\text{-phen})]$ requires : Mo, 22.96%; N, 8.6%, Cl, 16.98%.

7. μ -2,9-dimethyl-*o*-phenanthroline-dioxo-tetrachloro-bis(picolinato)-dimolybdenum(V) (*Dark chocolate*) was prepared as above using 2,9-dimethyl-*o*-phenanthroline (0.21 g) in place of 5-nitro-*o*-phenanthroline. Found : Mo, 22.86%; N, 27%; Cl, 16.97%. $[\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_2\text{Cl}_4(\text{pic})_2(2,9\text{-dimethyl-}o\text{-phen})]$ requires : Mo, 23.5%; N, 6.8%; Cl, 17.4%.

8. μ -5-nitro-*O*-phenanthroline-dioxo-tetrachloro-bis(oxinato)-dimolybdenum(V) (*Dark chocolate*)—Oxine (0.35 g), dissolved in 5.0 ml. anhydrous ethanol was added to the filtered solution of oxypentachloro molybdate (0.65 g) dissolved in 15.0 ml. anhydrous alcohol. Immediately, an intense red solution developed. This was refluxed for 15 minutes when the solution turned green and a dark:green compound yielded (identified previously as $[\text{MoOCl}(\text{oxine})_2]$). This compound was separated and the clear filtrate was refluxed with 5-nitro-*o*-phenanthroline (0.2 g) dissolved in 10.0 ml. anhydrous alcohol, when deep maroon shining crystals formed. It was cooled, filtered, washed several times with anhydrous ethanol and finally dried over CaCl_2 . Found : Mo, 22.2%; N, 8.3%; Cl, 16.7%. $[\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_2\text{Cl}_4(\text{oxine})_2(5\text{-nitro } O\text{-phen})]$ requires Mo, 21.7%; N, 7.9%; Cl, 16.2%.

Analytical Methods :

Molybdenum content was determined either by decomposing the complex with equal volumes of concentrated H_2SO_4 and HNO_3 or with alkali hydrogen peroxide. Then after adjusting the pH, molybdenum was precipitated with oxine as $[\text{MoO}_2(\text{oxine})_2]$. The precipitate was dissolved in hot alkali, cooled, reprecipitated with dilute H_2SO_4 , dried and weighed as $\text{MoO}_2(\text{oxine})_2$.

Estimation of chlorides was made by decomposing the complex with alkali-hydrogen peroxide, acidified with HNO_3 and precipitated as AgCl . This was dissolved in dilute NH_4OH , reprecipitated with dilute HNO_3 , dried and weighed as AgCl .

Nitrogen was estimated by combustion technique.

The magnetic moments were determined by the Gouy method using a semi-micro Mettler Balance for measuring the difference in weight with a field strength of 8.44×10^3 gauss. Diamagnetic corrections were taken from Selwood⁶.

Oxidation state of molybdenum in the complexes was determined by dissolving a known weight of the sample in excess acidified ferric alum solution under magnetic stirring in a stoppered flask. After complete dissolution (which sometimes needed more than an hour), the ferrous content was determined by usual permanganate titration. A blank was also run taking a similar weight of the heterocyclic ligands.

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